

**MOTIVE OF CHILDREN'S SUFFERING IN THE STORY
Z. PRILEPIN “WHITE SQUARE”**

Mavlyanova Leylo

1st Year Student Of The Faculty Of Russian Language And Literature

Jizzakh State Pedagogical

University Named After A. Kadyri, Uzbekistan

Scientific Supervisor:

Isaeva Yuliya Pavlovna

Abstract: The article is devoted to the motive of childhood suffering in Z. Prilepin’s story “White Square”. Z. Prilepin, using contemporary material, raises the topic of childhood suffering in the world, thinking about timeless questions of existence.

Key words: Prilepin, “Sin”, “White Square”, Zakharka, Sasha, memory, nostalgia, childhood, symbol, image of a child, motive of childhood suffering

Zakhar Prilepin - prose writer, publicist, musician. Winner of the “National Bestseller”, “SuperNatsBest” and “Yasnaya Polyana” awards. Author of the novels “The Abode”, “Sankya”, “Black Monkey”, “Pathologies”, as well as the famous novel in short stories “Sin”, recognized as the best book of the decade.

“Sin” is reflection and love, fun and courage, boyishness dissolved in blood, and happiness, tight as a sail, ringing summer and greedy joy of life. Poetic, subtle, poignant, very personal story of a hero named Zakharka.

A small provincial town and a quiet village, lost in the troubled nineties. The imperceptible transformation of a boy into a man: from barefoot childhood with discoveries and tragedies that last a lifetime, to tender and fragile youth with the first unrequited love, to the drunken and bad frenzy of youth, to surprised

fatherhood - with responsibility for his children and his woman.

After reading his story “White Square”, you can understand the essence of friendship, nostalgia, which comes gradually with our growing up. We are nostalgic about our childhood, about how we walked and played with the same carefree children like ourselves.

The story describes the completely ridiculous death of the teenage child Sashka. He, according to the author, “was extraordinary”; unlike other boys, he considered the younger guys also people with equal rights, and not “petty” who did not understand anything. From the very beginning, we feel sympathy for Sashka, in addition to the descriptions, this is helped by the introduction of anti-heroes into the story - the Chebryakov brothers, hooligans, whom Sashka, one of the very few, could fight back with words.

At the same time, the feeling that something is about to happen to him spreads throughout the story; this is achieved through the narrator’s mental dialogues with Sashka, the description of his strange, scary face, and also by the fact that he is always mentioned only in the past tense.

It seems that nature is also preparing the reader for his death. Throughout the story there is absolutely no sun or color, so the world appears in black and white. Animals are also presented only atonic. A crow or raven is a messenger of death, a constant companion of any creatures of the underworld, a goat, considered one of the incarnations of the devil, “tragedy” translated from Greek as “goat song.” These “goat sayings”, supposedly heard by the author, seem to foretell trouble.

The main essence of the story is the nostalgia of childhood. The story itself is the memories of little Zakharka, from playing hide and seek until the death of his friend Sashka. Zakhar remembers his childhood friends. The power of nostalgia is too strong and it occupies the hero's mind. He remembered the quiet Sasha, who was the youngest in the company of friends, and who was rarely noticed. Zakhar understands: he wants to be like his friend Sasha. Time flies forward, and much

can no longer be returned.

The issue itself also concerns nostalgia, but also shows problems such as ignoring people. In the story, these people are Sashka's parents and grandmother.

The first proof of Zakharka's mother's ignoring: "Mom. I want to tell you about the game. Now, son. And another glass of tea. And three cubes of sugar. Where are you going, mom? I want to tell you now. Well, I'm gone" [1, p. 62].

Second evidence: "Sashka's parents thought that he stayed with his grandmother. Grandmother thought that he had gone home to his parents" [1, p. 63].

Animals play a big role in the story: goats and crows. Tragedy - the goat's song: "the goats were interested in the boys' games" - danger always followed the boys during their games. "I ran, ran, ran - and still received a not at all painful, but very offensive push..." [1, p.60] - the tragedy seemed to warn the boys, knocking them to the ground, jabbing them in the back, that things could happen much worse than an offensive fall. But Sasha saddles the goat, not taking the warning seriously. The crow now becomes the main one - a symbol of death, whose cawing is not good. The boy skillfully imitates her. He is a child, a boy, and thereby denies the existence of such things as death in the world. An interesting detail: it was Sashka's grandmother who had the goats, because when he didn't return, the parents thought that the boy had stayed with her, so they didn't look for their son while he was dying in the refrigerator.

Sashka is a wonderful, kind person, he dies very undeservedly and absurdly, and although there is anxiety, it takes on the form of death only at the end. Until the very end you don't understand what they are talking about, these conversations between the author and Sashka, what is happening to him. We do not understand, as the narrator understands, that he is dead, but for us he is alive. Other characters in this story also become alive. The guys, their emotions and relationships are described in an unusually realistic, life-like way. Because of this, at the end of the

story you feel not just pity (well, a literary hero died, so what?), but shock, since it is not an abstract hero who dies, but the real Sashka, to whom I have already become attached. The effect of reality is enhanced by the coincidence of the name of the real author and the hero of the story.

Also in the work we can notice the image “White Square”; it’s not for nothing that the story is called that. There is a white square painted on the “selmag door”, where the children knocked and shouted “Forget me!”, as well as a square refrigerator, Sanya’s frozen mouth in the shape of a square, square white sugar that Zakhara’s mother put in her son’s tea.

The square is the second component of the complex color image contained in the name, one of the most common geometric symbols. The square is closely associated with the symbolism of the number four, for which it serves as a graphic symbol, as well as the cross, including the oblique cross and the swastika. In fact, the square contains the structure of the cross within itself, and can often act as its symbolic analogue.

In this story, the square is compared precisely with the sign of the way of the cross - the martyrdom of the boy and the torment of conscience of his younger friend.

In conclusion, we can conclude that the story focuses on the motif of memory and nostalgia, as well as childhood trauma. The key images of the work are images of children.

"White Square" is dedicated to the power of human memory and unforgettable childhood.

REFERENCES:

1. Prilepin Z. Sin (collection). M: "AST", 2007. P. 200. ISBN 978-5-17-086418-8

